

THE DEVELOPMENT OF A CARBON FIBRE VIOLIN

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SUMMARY

A composite violin potentially offers robustness and consistency that cannot be matched by wooden instruments. This paper describes a programme of experimental and analytical work to develop vibration and acoustic characteristics to match high quality instruments and considers structures and manufacturing methods necessary to achieve a modern violin.

Violin, composite, carbon, sandwich, vibration, acoustic, manufacture

Introduction

This project began following a discussion with a local violinmaker. He was interested in the possibility of a composite violin to overcome a number of shortcomings that he saw in the conventional instrument. In particular, a wooden instrument is extremely fragile, and very sensitive to humidity. A further issue is that due to the variability of individual pieces of wood, and the nature of the hand process, it is not possible to build instruments of consistent tone quality. The use of composite materials, particularly carbon – epoxy systems, would go some way towards mitigating these problems. A final advantage is that the cost of the carbon fibre components should be less than the very expensive woods that are conventionally used, and the manufacturing methods are much less time consuming than those for wood.

There is a considerable body of literature on the acoustics and the vibration characteristics of violins and their individual components. On the whole this has been led by Carleen Hutchins and J E McLennan [e.g. 1 and 2] However, almost all of this work is looking back at how modern makers can reproduce the sound of instruments made by the Italian masters of the 17th and 18th century. There is almost no literature on the serious use of alternative materials in the making of a high quality violin.

The idea of the carbon fibre violin is not in itself novel. In the 1980s Hutchins in collaboration with Hercules produced an experimental hybrid, using a uni-directional carbon fibre laminate [3]. There is no further information on either its sound or its construction. Luis and Clark produce carbon violas and cellos [4] although there is no evidence of any supporting research and there are few reports of their sound quality.

The work described in this paper attempts to address the issues of the desirable dynamic properties of composite violin components and to consider the appropriate material systems and manufacturing processes that might achieve these qualities and meet the initial requirements of the luthier. The objective is to produce a violin that might be used by a serious student and possibly a professional at least in their early career.

The Violin Pattern.

There are many pattern of violin that could be used as the basis of this work. In this case the design was based on the Guarneri violins, produced in Cremona, Italy in the 16th and 17th centuries [5]. Specifically, this is the “Lord Wilton” violin of 1742. The Wilton was chosen because it is a pattern of unimpeachable provenance and there exists some detail of its shape and form [6]. To some extent this made life difficult, as many of the Stradivarius and Guarneri violins are asymmetrical, leading to issues in modelling the shape and manufacturing the moulds.

The initial intention had been to use some form of remote scanning to capture the shape of the violin panels digitally. In reality the techniques available all involved surface preparation or contact that was unacceptable to owners of valuable and possibly rare violins. In the end the shape was modelled manually by measurement and the use of a poster giving the main dimensions of the “Lord Wilton”.

The Strategy.

The first problem in producing a quality violin in an unconventional is deciding where to start. The team developed a strategy fairly early on involving the following steps;

- Manufacture and test flat panels representing the front of the violin.
 - Frequency spectrum analysis
 - Chladni nodal line testing
- Manufacture and test shaped front panels.
 - Frequency spectrum analysis
 - Chladni nodal line testing
 - Laser vibrometer testing
- Testing the “best” front panel on an otherwise wooden violin.
- Design and manufacture of an “all carbon” violin.
- Design of an all-carbon electric violin to develop the manufacturing methods.

The objective of this work is to gradually build the body of knowledge and understanding necessary to produce the final instrument.

Flat plate testing.

The first phase of the project was to manufacture and test a number of flat plates to see if it was possible to even get close to the normal requirements of the luthier (violin maker). A typical luthier will assess a panel by supporting it at an anti-node and tapping it. He will look at the second and fifth node in the spectrum. The frequency of the second mode should be about 316 Hz and the fifth should be about twice that value

[7]. A second method that is often used is the Chladni test, where the panel is driven by a loud speaker and the vibration patterns are indicated by powder that migrates to the nodal positions. It should be said that there is not absolute agreement over this. While authorities such as Hutchins and Jansson [8] argue for precise and definite frequencies and patterns, Attwood [9] suggests that it is more important that the plate be dynamically “lively” rather than having a precise set of properties. In his paper, he looks at the ratio of sonic velocity in the material to density, and draws the conclusion that an ideal material would be balsa wood if it could be made to carry the substantial loads that are imposed upon the body of the violin.

The problem with trying to replicate exactly the dynamic properties that the luthier will consider to be ideal is in the nature of the materials. In some respects, wood is nature’s composite. The grain in a violin panel is arranged to be along the length of the violin. In principle this is possible with composite, using uni-directional material. However, the ratios of longitudinal to transverse moduli are very much higher in carbon fibre than in wood and it was considered that the properties of the resultant panel would be so different as to make any comparison invalid. All of the panels for the acoustic violin were from woven epoxy pre-impregnated systems at $120 \text{ gm} / \text{m}^2$ giving a thickness of about $0.125 \text{ mm} / \text{ply}$.

A series of flat sandwich panels were made giving variation in:

- Skin thickness -1, 2 and 3 plies
- Skin orientations - $0/90^\circ$ and $\pm 45^\circ$
- Core thickness – 1.5 mm and 3.0 mm
- Core material – balsa wood and polymer foam (Rohacell)

Tap testing the first two panels showed an immediate anomaly. Both had a 3.0mm thick foam core while the first had 2 ply (0.25 mm) skins and the second 4 ply (0.5 mm) skins. With skins that are very much thinner than the panel thickness and a very low density core a first approximation would suggest that the two panels would have similar values of mass / density and should, therefore, exhibit similar dynamic properties. However, the skin with the thicker skins demonstrated a fundamental natural frequency of about twice that of the second panel. This suggests that the panels are not behaving as a single sandwich panel, but as two separate, thin skins. The first indication is that the amplitude of the vibration is so small that the core does not transmit shear forces between the skins, but simply fixes the distance between them (figure 1).

The results of the Chladni testing of the flat plates was varied. Most showed strong and clear patterns (figure 2), while some failed to show any clear modes at all.

In general the Chladni results correlated well with the major peaks from the spectrum analysis. An interesting observation was that the nodal patterns shown on the surface of the panels was insensitive to the profiling of the panel core material or the thickness of the carbon skins. On the original flat panels the core was profiled such that at the positions of the “f” holes, bridge and sound post the core was feathered away and additional plies of carbon were added. These were quite large features, yet the Chladni patterns showed no indication of being disturbed by them.

Attempts at modelling the panels at a realistic level indicated that the effort and resource necessary to model violin panels with the necessary subtlety would be beyond the scope of this project. It is anticipated that this will be investigated further at a later stage.

Overall, the results of the flat plate testing suggested that it was possible to manufacture panels demonstrating a wide variation of dynamic properties and that the panels could be tuned to achieve the required behaviour. The conclusion was that it should be possible to produce profiled panels representative of those on a high quality violin that could be tuned to meet the requirements of luthiers and players.

Testing of shaped panels.

The body of a violin comprises three major components, the back, the rib, which is the spacer between the two main panels, and the front. It is generally believed that the quality of sound of a violin is primarily dependent on the front panel. The objective of this part of the programme was to test a number of panels based on the flat panel results. The “best” panel would be fitted to an otherwise wooden violin of known quality so that experienced players could evaluate the resulting instrument. In addition to the spectrum and Chladni testing, a laser vibrometer technique was used to give a further insight to the behaviour of the panels. This was a prelude to further studies on panels vibration and the dynamics of the complete instrument.

Following the results of the flat plate testing, the range of front panels was simplified. All comprised skins of two plies of carbon pre-preg and a core of 1.5 mm thick balsa wood or foam, or were solid panels of six plies of carbon. A traditional violin has a reinforcement rib, known as a bass bar, which effectively runs under the bass string on the inside of the front panel. Since these have a relatively minor effect on the vibration of a wooden panel, the bass bar was not included on the sandwich panel, due to their very high panel stiffness. However, the solid carbon panels did include a bass bar due to their much lower inherent stiffness. The manufacture of these panels is described in a later section.

The dynamic properties of the shaped panels broadly followed that of the flat panels. The Chladni testing is a little more difficult to interpret due to the tendency of the powder to collect in the bottom of the panel. Chladni tests and the laser vibrometer results indicated very similar nodal patterns (figure 3).

As a result of the tests two panels were chosen for the hybrid violin evaluation. The first was a sandwich panel comprising two skins, each of 0/90 carbon and a core of 1.5mm thick balsa wood. The second was a “solid” carbon panel of six plies, each at +/- 45. Only the second was fitted with a bass bar. The first was selected because it was acoustically lively and close to the properties recommended by Attwood [8], and the second because its low panel stiffness gave it properties closer to wood in the longitudinal direction than any other panel.

The Evaluation of the Hybrid Violin

Within the team there had been considerable debate as to how to evaluate the violin. Although a number of advanced techniques could have been applied, the question was what the desired or ideal characteristics would be.

A conventional violin would be judged on the opinion of the players and audience. At this stage in the project, this is the approach that has been taken. Fortunately expert players and the professional violinmaker were available for the evaluation.

The perception of the violin is complicated by the style of the player, the bow and the room in which it is played. As far as has been practical, all the variables other than the violin itself have remained constant. The test violin was originally fitted with a wooden front, so its quality is known. It was then fitted with the carbon sandwich from (figure 4). Traditional animal based glues as used in violin making will not adhere to carbon fibre. It was necessary to fit a very thin plywood gasket round the edge of the panel to allow the carbon to be bonded to the gasket with epoxy resin and the gasket to the wooden violin body with conventional glues.

The first test was slightly disappointing, as there seemed to be a slight banjo quality when the strings were plucked. However, when bowed the sound was much better. One surprising result was that the carbon front produced a much louder sound than the wooden original. One would first expect the greater stiffness of the carbon panel to result in lower amplitudes from a given driving force, hence a lower volume. The treble strings were said to exhibit some unpleasant high frequency harmonics. There were no dead notes where the instrument failed to respond. The results were felt to be encouraging, but there was substantial room for improvement.

The test on the solid carbon panel were much more encouraging. The sound was still much louder than a conventional violin. The players described the sound of the bass strings as warm, similar to a viola. Following the formal testing the players tried the violin in a lecture theatre with acoustic properties much closer to a concert hall. Here the harsh sound of the treble strings was much less noticeable. The instrument was considered to be quite playable and close to the expected "advanced student" quality.

Manufacture

Manufacturing these panels turned out to be more complex than expected. The intention had been to use a laser scanning system to capture a digital definition of the shape of the panels then to use rapid manufacture to produce the tools. It was not possible to use these systems for a number of reasons, so ended up manually modelling the form of the Lord Wilton violin based on published data [6]. The data files were then used to produce the mould shape directly in MDF on a CNC milling machine. The moulds were then rubbed down by hand, primed and spray painted to give a highly polished finish (figure 5).

The parts were made from 0.125 mm thick woven carbon pre-preg and, where appropriate, core material. The pre-preg is laid onto the moulds, bagged up and then cured in an oven under vacuum.

Once the parts are taken from the mould it is necessary to cut them out and trim them. Some parts, such as the neck, could easily be trimmed by hand, but others, particularly the front with its "f" holes, were much more problematic. The solution applied in this case was to use a multi-axis water-jet cutter that we have available at the University of Nottingham (figure 6).

In order to produce the complete carbon fibre violin, the following parts are required;

- Front panel
- Back panel
- Rib
- Left and right halves of the neck and peg box.

At this stage of the project a wooden fingerboard had been retained so that the violin feels as normal as possible to the player.

Each part was modelled from the available data [5 and 6] then machined and finished as described above. The kit of parts is then bonded with epoxy adhesives and simple jigs are used to locate the parts.

The Electric Violin

At the start of the project there was no certainty that a quality acoustic violin could be produced at all or how long it would take to develop acceptable panels. In parallel with this project an electric violin has been produced. The reason behind this is that the electric is far less subject to the natural conservatism of the conventional luthier and could be produced much faster. This meant that most of the design and manufacturing issues could be addressed before the acoustic panels had been perfected and any lessons fed back into the acoustic programme. As far as possible components such as the neck, fingerboard and bridge are identical on both the acoustic and the electric violin (figure 7). The electric violin showed that the carbon structure was entirely viable – and it also sounds good in its own right.

Conclusions.

While it is too early to claim that we have produced and demonstrated a carbon fibre violin that would be attractive in all respects to advanced students and young professionals, it is reasonable to claim that we have developed a reasonable violin and a suite of technologies that will allow the components to be further developed to achieve the full objective.

The following conclusions can be drawn at this stage;

- The evaluation of the hybrid violin indicates the viability of a fully playable, high quality carbon fibre violin.
- The frequency spectrum analysis and Chladni methods are entirely suitable for composite construction.
- The composite violin will meet the durability objectives.
- The higher natural frequencies of the carbon panels (compared with wood) give greater scope for tuning the panels to meet the exacting requirements of the luthier, player and audience.
- The addition of the laser vibrometer to the suite of analytical methods has greatly increased the understanding of the vibration and tuning of the panels. It will also enable the analysis of critical groups of components and the complete instrument.

Further Work.

What the project has achieved so far is to show considerable promise. To take this further and produce the complete violin, the following steps will be necessary.

- Develop the laser vibrometer method to help the understanding of the relationships of the main components. For example, does the neck play a role and is the mass of the scroll important?
- The work has already indicated new composite structures that might be used to tune-out the high frequencies on the treble strings. These will be developed further.
- Modelling and simulation work was dismissed at an early stage in the programme due to the time that it would take to develop it to the point that it could make a significant contribution to the understanding and design of the violin. However, if the technology is to develop, then suitable modelling methods must be developed and evaluated.
- While the current tooling and assembly methods are adequate for low numbers, it will be necessary to improve the manufacturing technology to make the violin easier to make by a relatively un-skilled workforce.

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Figure 1: Flat plate vibration spectrum analysis. Panel "A" has four ply, 0/90 0.125mm thick skins, and Panel "B" has two. Both have a 3.0mm thick foam core.

Figure 2: Typical Chladni test on a flat panel. Panel “A” as figure 1.

Figure 3: Comparison of Chladni and Laser Vibrometer results for a shaped panel. Two 0/90 ply skins and 1.5mm balsa core at 834 Hz.

Figure 4: Karen playing the hybrid violin

Figure 5: Typical tooling and moulded part.

Figure 6: Example of a water-jet cut panel

Figure 7: The electric violin